

EIC User Group Newsletter

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NEWS

- Change in the EICUG **Steering Committee**: Rik Yoshida, former representative of JLab, has been appointed Director of the High Energy Division at Argonne National Lab. With his departure from JLab, **Rolf Ent** will take over as **new representative of JLab**
- The [last EICUG annual meeting](#) was held on July 22-26, in Paris, with 151 participants. It featured 4 topical sessions on new advances in the physics as well as accelerator and detector R&D related to the Electron-Ion Collider project, 2 specific parallel sessions, a poster session, a session dedicated to reports from the various Working Groups, a tutorial on EIC software simulation, and a session for the IB meeting. In this last session, the **EICUG** voted for the date and location of the **next annual meetings**: the **2020** one will be held in **Miami**, 3-7 Aug. 2020, hosted by Florida International Univ.; the **2021** one will be held in **Warsaw**, hosted by Univ. of Warsaw and the National Centre for Nuclear Research (NCBJ).
- The Steering Committee announced to the EIC User Group and to all IB members a [new initiative](#) for organizing a 12-18 month intensive study of the EIC physics and detector concepts, seeking to build on the 2014 EIC White Paper and the EIC Detector Requirements and R&D Handbook and to finalize the work in a published summary in the form of the CERN Yellow Reports.

- The **next remote IB meeting** will be held on Oct. 10th, 2019, starting at 10:00am U.S. EDT. The agenda will focus on discussion of the organization of the 12-18 month intensive study of the EIC physics and detector concepts, described in the previous item.
- The **next quarterly meeting** will be held on Oct. 24th, 2019.

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- A new **Conference & Talks Committee** is in place from Sept. 1st, 2019, until Aug. 31st, 2020:
 - ★ Ralf Seidl, Chair (RIKEN; agreed for 2nd term)
 - ★ Barbara Pasquini (Univ. Pavia and INFN-Pavia; agreed for 2nd term)
 - ★ Carlos Munoz Camacho (Orsay; agreed for second term)
 - ★ Sevil Salur (Rutgers; first term)
 - ★ Dmitry Romanov (JLab; first term)
- In **2019**, so far there have been **18 invitations for EIC talks** sent to the Conference & Talks Committee by organizers of various international conferences and workshops; see the detailed list at <http://eicug.org/web/events/previous> . If in this list some invited presentation is missing, or if someone has been directly invited by some organizers to give a talk on the EIC project, please contact the Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org for the purpose of updating this statistics.
- For upcoming conferences and workshops listed at <http://eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> , there are **currently no EIC talks** appointed. If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

NEWS from ELECTION and NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- A new **Election and Nomination Committee** is in place from Sept. 1st, 2019, until Aug. 31st, 2020:
 - ★ Paul Newman (Univ. Birmingham; agreed for second term)
 - ★ Christian Weiss, Chair (JLab; agreed for second term)
 - ★ Abhay Deshpande (SBU/BNL; first term)
 - ★ Yuri Kovchegov (OSU; first term)
 - ★ Marta Ruspa, Vice Chair (Univ. P.O. and INFN-Torino; first term)
- During the last EICUG meeting in Paris, the IB Chair announced the final result of the election for **Chair, Vice Chair, and EU Representative** of the **EICUG Steering Committee** :
 - ★ Bernd Surrow confirmed Chair for a second term
 - ★ Richard Milner elected Vice Chair, first term
 - ★ Daniël Boer confirmed EU Representative for a second term

The 65% of eligible Institutions participated in the election of Chair and Vice Chair (118/182), while the 76% participated in the EU Representative one (47/62).

- In **October 2019**, the term of Ernst Sichtermann as “At Large Member” of the EICUG Steering Committee will end. Further news will follow from the Committee about organization and dates of the corresponding elections.

EIC on MEDIA

- **New article** by Rik Yoshida and Abhay Deshpande on Scientific American:
The Deepest Recesses of The Atom,
[Scientific American June 2019](#), p.32

- The article has been translated and published on the Italian version of the journal, *Le Scienze*, **accompanied by a short comment** by Alessandro Bacchetta, Andrea Bressan and Marco Radici on the involvement of the Italian community in the EIC project:
Italia all'avanguardia nell'Electron-Ion Collider, *Le Scienze* Agosto 2019, p. 32

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

[MENU 2019](#), Pittsburgh (PA-USA), 2-7 June 2019

[PHOTON 2019](#), LNF Frascati (Italy), 3-7 June 2019

[XLVII International Meeting on Fundamental Physics](#), Madrid (Spain), 3-7 June 2019

[Strangeness in Quark Matter \(SQM 19\)](#), Bari (Italy), 10-15 June 2019

[18th Conference on Elastic and Diffractive Scattering](#), Quy Nhon (Vietnam), 23-29 June 2019

[Initial Stages 2019](#), New York (USA), 24-28 June 2019

[EIC ad-hoc meeting on detector and physics simulations](#), BNL Upton (NY - USA), 10 July 2019

[EIC User Group meeting 2019](#), Paris (France), 22-26 July 2019

[27th International Nuclear Physics Conference \(INPC 2019\)](#), Glasgow (Scotland), 28 July - 2 August 2019

[29th Conference on Lepton and Photon Interactions \(LP2019\)](#), Toronto (Canada), 5-10 August 2019

[Hadron 2019](#), Guilin (China), 16-21 August 2019

[8th International Conference on New Frontiers in Physics \(ICNFP 19\)](#), Kolymbari (Greece), 21-30 August 2019

[The 11th Circum-Pan-Pacific Symposium on High Energy Spin Physics](#), Miyazaki (Japan), 27-30 August 2019

[POETIC 2019](#), Berkeley (CA - USA), 16-20 September 2019

[Light Cone 2019](#), Palaiseau (France), 16-20 September 2019

[EIC Software meeting and GEANT4 Technical Forum](#), JLab Newport News (VA - USA), 24 September 2019

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

[13th European Research Conference on Electromagnetic Interactions with Nucleons and Nuclei \(EINN 2019\)](#), Paphos (Cyprus), 27 October - 2 November 2019

[CHEP 2019](#), Adelaide (Australia), 3-8 November 2019

[Quark Matter 2019](#), Wuhan (China), 4-8 November 2019

[EIC Streaming Readout workshop](#), BNL Upton (NY - USA), 13-15 November 2019

[Forward Physics and QCD at LHC](#), Guanajuato (Mexico), 18-23 November 2019

[MCEGs for future ep and eA facilities](#), Vienna (Austria), 20-22 November 2019

[Resummation, Evolution, Factorization \(REF 2019\)](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 November 2019

[International workshop on QCD with EIC \(QEIC\)](#), Bombay (India), 4-7 January 2020

[Winter Workshop on Nuclear Dynamics](#), Puerto Vallarta (Mexico), 1-7 March 2019

[DIS 2020](#), Brooklyn (NY - USA), 23-27 March 2020

[QCD Evolution 2020](#), Los Angeles (CA - USA), 27 April - 1 May 2020

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020

[Hard Probes](#), Austin (TX - USA), 1-6 June 2020

[40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#), Prague (Czech Republic), 30 July - 5 August 2020

[Photonuclear Gordon Conference](#), Holderness (NH - USA), 9-14 August 2020

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#), Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25 September 2020

Please, have a look also at the following link:

<http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html>